

Translation and Literature Development in Northern Nigeria

Suleiman Adamu Sarbi

Department of African Languages and Cultures, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

Abstract

Translation, as a cross-cultural and bilingual activity is paramount in the development of any nation. Many countries worldwide, having discovered the significance of translation in the all-round development of human life, employ its services for their educational and scientific aspirations. As a dynamic phenomenon, science and science education as well as other human arts such as literature have a cross-cultural experience in the most dynamic form. It has, from earlier time to date, always been developed freely by some peoples and the idea discovered through translation, emulated and employed by others. The translation of human knowledge becomes the experience, and therefore, calls the attention of various peoples across the globe, such as Egyptians Persians, Arabs, Europeans, Japanese and Chinese and of course Africans etc. The aim of this paper is to study, discover and present the role of translation in the development of literature in northern Nigeria. The methodology used revolves around extensive and intensive readings to discover literary activities pioneered by means of translation. The conclusion is in conformity with the fact that there are various literary works in all branches of literature that were composed by employing the service of translation. The paper discloses, in comparison, the literature works compiled and their original sources as evidences.

Introduction

It is pertinent and cross-experience that hardly can any development in any case, manifest without the role of language. Indeed, each Language contains certain development of its users (people) which are not known to other people as a result of cultural distinction. However, by employing the service of translation, all human development such as knowledge, skills and ideas had; over the years, been extended from some peoples to others. Indeed the results of the extension were positive across the world. This made it necessary for conscious people, governments and universities across the globe to establish centres, institutes, associations and bureaus as well as companies for translation and interpretation. In addition to that, other languages based business services are provided all in order to find out various developments in other cultures and render it into the languages and cultures of the needy people. This may be done by invention or adaptation. No doubt, the outcomes are fruitful as they led and continue to lead to the development of many countries. The significant role played by translation in the all-round development of man leads to the development of theoretical frameworks in the field of translation. Moreover, the concept of cultural encounter all over the world, especially from the 3rd and 4th centuries, discloses the significance of translation in the development of literature. Indeed, when people of different cultures come and live together, there is likelihood of imitating, and therefore, influencing one another. This influence will definitely include the exchange of literary aspects of their cultures. This paper brings the general populace to the knowledge on the contribution of translation in the development and spread of human literature through cultural exchange in Northern Nigeria. Various examples are assembled and presented to support the presentation. Before then, the definition and classification of literature are paramount.

What is Literature?

Just as many other concepts, literature has been defined differently by different scholars at varying times. The definitions depend on the conceptual exposure and purpose of each scholar

in the circle. Some see it from general and academic point of view while others view it from the technical (specific field of study) perspective. And in each case, scholars disclose varying levels of perception and description. According to Webster (1993), for example, literature is “the writings of a period or of a country, especially those valued for their excellence; of style or form; all the books and articles on a subject – any printed matter.” This definition is in line with that of Devinne (1989) who defines literature as “written works that have lasting value and interest, printed material of any kind.” Then Moody (1987 in Arzai 2008:1) opines that “literature springs from our inborn love of telling a story, of arranging words in pleasing patterns, of expressing in words some specific aspects of human experiences.” Technically, however, literature refers to “an imaginative work of art designed and moulded in prosaic dramatic and verse form, each with its own peculiar and distinctive mode of execution” (Arzai 2008:1).

The Classification of Literature

In academic circle, literature is classified into two main sections, thus oral literature and written literature. Oral literature, such as folklore, encompasses proverbs, riddles and joke, fairy tales, etc., while the written one encompasses prose, play and poetry. (Sarvi 2016:74) Definitely, all the branches of literature are developed and spread by means of translation.

Background

The traditional and modern literatures of many communities are transmitted to other ethnic groups by means of translation. The work of translation, moreover, penetrated all the arms of oral and written literature. It crossed into oral-song, proverbs, superstition, stories and folktales for oral literature and into prose, drama and poetry for written literature. This is evident in the numerous works which will be examined subsequently. Lechner (2006:13) testified that:

The first English purveyor of fine translation was the first English poet; Geoffrey Chaucer. By his time both Italian and French had acquired status as languages fit for a literature of entertainment, if not for learned works. Chaucer, whose language was still regarded as barbarous in 14th century Western Europe, therefore, required three foreign tongues, not one, to read the fashionable writers of his day: Boethius in Latin, Giovanni Boccaccio in Italian and the Roman de la rose in French. Chaucer freely adapted Boccaccio in his own Knight’s Tale and Troilus and Criseyde, began translation of the Roman, and translated the whole of Boethius called *Grant Translateur* by the French poet Eustache Deschamps, his contemporary. Most of Medieval literature was based on free adaptation.

The Plutarch (1579) of Sir Thomas North had two versions, the Greek and French versions. The French version was translated by Jacques Amyot. So also the Montaigne Essay (1603) of the Italian refugee John Florio was loosely discursive where Montaigne was both subtle and taut (Lechner 2006:13). Another reputable translator of the century was Philemon Holland. He was a translation figure who rendered “The Million and more words of Pliny’s Natural History (1601)” in just a year. He also translated “Livy, Xenophon, Suetonius” and Plutarch “Morelia (1603).” Holland was greatly respected for his text than any of his contemporary, such as North or Florio. He was credited for translation activities par excellence. It went to the extent that Fuller named him the *Translator General* in his age (Lechner 2006:13).

Like all Elizabethans, Holland engaged into the circumlocution procedure of translation in which his prose writing requires more than twice the number of words of the original. In fact, this is one of the characteristics of literature translation. That is, expanding or slopping the content of the original to suit the culture and grammatical structure of the receptor language. According to Lechner (2006:13), the last of these Elizabethans was Sir Thomas Urquhart who actually wrote during the Commonwealth. He translated the first three books of Rabelais (1653-

1693). He widely expanded his French original without digressing from its content. Both Aeneid 1697 of Dryden and Iliad (1715) and Odyssey (1725) a long exciting journey of Pope were translated poems which were more or less the imitation of the national epics. During the 18th Century, Alexander Pope and William Cowper contributed in the literary translation by translating *Songs of Homer* from Greek to English. Likewise, George Chapman translated the *Songs of Homer* to Latin. This influenced William Shakespeare in writing his famous *Song of Sonnet*.

The missionaries also contributed in the translation of Nigerian literary work into English. Those which are worthy of mention are those from the south western states. These include the Ozziddi Saga by J. P. Clark-Beke deremo from Ijaw (Izon), Wole Soyinka's *The forest of a Thousand Demons* from the Yoruba author Fagunwa, and *The Calabash of Wisdom And Other Stories* from Igbo (Ebenezer 2003:46).

Translation and Literature Development in Northern Nigeria

When the question of language and cultural contact is discussed, a point should be made clear of the sources of the contact. The point of mission, exploration, colonialism, wars and battles, migration, trades and the need for scholarship compelled different tribes to live together for their respective objectives. It is important to note that the movement of the people is all over the world and cross-cultural.

When these people move from one area to another, they always move with their literature (oral or written). And wherever they are, they make use of their literary work. While moving out, they must leave the blueprint of their literary work there, and usually go with the literary work of the area. This is a cultural or literary exchange. It can be intentional or unintentional. By so doing, in just a short period of time, world literary activities crossed into different cultures and were mostly adopted. This went to the extent that one finds a single tale, story, superstition or proverb in various languages. Sometimes one could not even trace the real origin of a certain tale or story etc. unless by historical perspective. This is because whenever a tale crosses different cultures, each culture strives to indigenize the tale or the story into it. Here the immense contribution of translation becomes understandable.

If the tales and stories of some people will be adapted into the literature of other people, it obviously leads to literary development of the people. This is because, after being indigenized, the tales and stories, etc. will be an addition to those already in the culture. Moreover, this will improve in widening the experience of the people hosting the literary art.

Translation became a prominent linguistic device used in forming various literary works. Many people translated the literary works of other people into their languages. Likewise, their own indigenous literature was translated into many other languages. That is why, as already stated, a single story is found in different languages, and each language is proud of it. Take, for example, the tale *Panchatantra*, which is an Indian tale, but which had been indigenized into Arabic as *Kalila Wa Dimna*, into Portuguese as *Kalila Et Dimna*, then into English as *Kalila And Dimna* and then into Hausa as *Kalila Da Dimna*. The same is true of *Hazar Afsanah*, which is an Iranian tale in the Farsi Persian language. The tale then became Arabic literature as *Alfu Laylah wa Laylah*. It then appeared in India as *One Thousand Stories, One Thousand Nights*. The tale has then, been adapted into English literary work in which it appeared as *One Thousand Nights and One Night*. Then Hausa indigenized the tale, with some Arabic traces, as *Dare Dubu Da Daya*. (Sarbi 2016:78)

In Nigeria and of course many other areas, it is discovered that many of the literary works were translated from other people's works. Sometimes, different tales and stories, written and oral, are used to form a book of prose, drama and even poetry. Abubakar Imam is considered to be

the great novelist, especially in Northern Nigeria. However, most of his works were compiled by making use of translation devices. His famous book, titled *Ruwan Bagaja*, which won the literary competition of 1933 was discovered to have been formed out of other literary works. These include: *The water of life* (A German tale) by Grimms, *Alfulaylah wa laylah* and *Maƙamatul Hariri* (Arabic) The book (*Ruwan Bagaja*) was then translated into English as *The Water of Cure* in 1978 by Amadu Ingawa. Likewise, *Magana Jari Ce* book 1, 2 and 3 by Abubakar Imam were formed out of other literary works. These books contain the moral, political, educational and economic aspects of human life. The books were compiled out of Arabic, German, Greek, Danish and other people's tales. For example, according to Bredsdorff (1975 cited in Abdullahi 1998:83), the literary works of Andersen, which contain 156 stories were translated from Danish into more than one hundred languages. These works were, first of all, translated into English in 1846. Imam used the English versions in forming some of his literary works. He used four different stories from *Andersen Fairy Tales* in writing four stories in *Magana Jari Ce* as follows: *The Flying Trunk*, which appeared in Vol. 4 in 1838, was translated as *Labarin Wani Bahindi*; *The Swineherd*, which features in Vol. 5 in 1842, was translated as *Labarin wanda ke Wulakanta Jama'a*; *Little Claus and Big Claus*, which was published in Vol.1 1835, was translated as *Rama Cuta ga Macuci Ibada (Telu Fari da Telu Baƙi)*; and *Emperor's New Clothes* published in Vol. 3 in 1837, was translated as *Labarin Sususu da Shashasha* (Abdullahi 1998:85).

So also *Aesop Fables* containing 383 stories were written and translated from Greek into more than 200 languages. Imam was expected to have used the English version, published in 1692 and revised in 1906, in writing some stories in *Magana Jari Ce* (Abdullahi 1998). These include: *Sai Bango ya Tsage Kadangarke Samun Wurin Shiga*. This story was translated from two sources: *Aesop Fables- A Father and his Sons* and *One Thousand Night and One Night- The Tale of a Sage and His Three Sons*. Moreover, the literary work of Jacob Grimm and Wilhelm Grimm, popularly known in the field of literature as the Brothers Grimm, containing more than 200 stories, were published in the German language as *Kinder-Und-Hause-Marchen* in 1812 and 1814 (Abdullahi 1998:89). Imam used the English version of the work published in 1823 to write some stories in *Magana Jari Ce*. These include: *Yusha'u na Narimi Dutse ba ka Fargaba* and *Kalala da Kalalatu* translated from the English version of *Grimms Fairy Tales* as *the story of the youth who went forth to learn what fear was*, and *Clever Gretel*, respectively (Sulaiman 2021:61).

In short, that is how Imam formed most of his excellent works. Abdullahi (1998:iv), in his abstract, discovered and, therefore, testified that: "Abubakar Imam was able to harness the different sources together by way of translation, adaptation and transmutation so that the sources became Hausanized."

If we go into poetic analysis, we shall discover that the metrical devices used in measuring a poem, technically known as prosody, were automatically adapted from Arabic to Hausa. Therefore, most of the Hausa poems are examined and measured by using such a loaned device. The device examines the syllable structures in different types of feet. Sa'id (1979) Aminu (1993) Zulyadaini (2005) and Sarfi (2007) worked on this device, which is studied and appreciated by Hausa literary speakers. Jibril (1981) technically translated and reviewed the Hausa poems *Waƙar Haɗa Kan Afirka* by Abubakar Ladan into English. The work is titled *O God Unite us Africans*. This review can fully and easily be appreciated by English literary speakers. The Jihadists under the leadership of Sheikh Usman Danfodiyo had, in the 19th century, written poems in both Arabic and Fulfulde, which were later translated into Hausa and have become part and parcel of Hausa literature. Mukoshy (1977 quoted in Jibril 1981:267) testified that:

Hausa formal poetry appears to have come into being as a result of translation of Fulfulde poems which in turn was modelled after Arabic poetry. The debt of Hausa poetry to Arabic poetry in terms of prosody alone is enormous and undeniable. It is obvious that Hausa formal poetry borrowed all its meters from Arabic; the correspondence between the two prosodic systems is one-to-one and therefore not mere coincidence.

The role of translation in literature development in the northern Nigeria appeared and therefore, evident in the contribution of Dandatti who published a book in 1978 titled *The Poetry, Life and Opinions of Sa'adu Zungur*. After the life history of Sa'adu Zungur, the writer continued to translate his popular poems into English as, *Heresy* for *waqar Bidi'a*, welcome to the soldiers' for *Maraba da soja*, *Careless Talk* for *wakar 'yanBaka* and lastly *The North, Republic or Monarchy* for *Arewa Jumhuriya ko Mulukiya*. These poems could be appreciated by English literalists.

The work of Neil Skinner is also remarkable and worth mention. He translated various oral folktales, folklores, proverbs and other branches of written literature, such as poetry and drama. In his book, *Anthology of Hausa literature in translation* (1980), Skinner translated Hausa poems and plays into English. Some of them include *Wakar Damina* by Na'ibi Suleiman Wali, as *Song of the Rainy Season* and the Hausa play titled *Uwar Gulma* (Sarfi, 2016:83).

On the part of drama, moreover, many plays were translated into various languages and became part of the literature of the receptor languages. *The Merchant of Venice* is the combination of two old folktales. The first is: *The story of the savage creditor who tries but fails to obtain a pound of human flesh as payment of a debt* and the second folktale was that of the lover who gains... These stories, crossed into plays were thought to be translated from Italian. However, the first story, which was already dramatized by Shakespeare as *The Merchant of Venice*, was later translated by Dahiru Idris in 1980 as *Matsolon Attajiri*. Likewise, *The Twelfth Night* by William Shakespeare was translated into Hausa as *Daren shaBiyu*, by Ibrahim Yaro Yahaya in 1971. Moreover, *Gandoki* is a book of prose written by Muhammad Bello (Walin Katsina) published first 1934 and the latest in 1980. The book was translated and published by NNPC as a controlled reader for primary schools. It is titled *The Adventures of the Warrior Gandoki*. Worthy of mention here, moreover, is *Animal Farm* by George Orwell, which was translated by Bala Funtua as *Gandun Dabbobi* (Sarfi 2016:84).

Conclusion

In the end, this paper examined the contributions of translation in the development of literature in northern Nigeria. The section discussed various segments of both the oral and written literature of various people and how they contributed in boosting other people's literature by means of translation.

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